

EARTH SCIENCES

STUDY OF *MIOGYPSINIDS* (OLIGOCENE-MIOCENE) IN THE KIRKUK AREA, NORTHEASTERN IRAQ

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Abstract

This study examines well-exposed outcrops and subsurface successions of bioclastic limestone from the Qara Chaugh–Dagh and Khabaz Well-3 sections in the Kirkuk area, northeastern Iraq. The carbonates were deposited within a shallow, open-marine setting during the Oligocene–Miocene (Chattian–Aquitanian). Larger foraminifera belonging to the Miogypsinidae are abundant throughout both the lower and upper parts of these carbonate sequences. Detailed biometric and morphological analyses of Miogypsinids indicate that the oldest representatives of the genus *Miogypsina* occur in the lower part of the Qara Chaugh–Dagh section, while the Khabaz Well-3 sequence is characterised by *Miogypsinoides complanata* and *M. formosensis*. Early Miocene assemblages dominated by *Miogypsina* s.s. are commonly associated with *Miogypsinoides*, many of which are closely related to *M. bantamensis*. Based on mean embryonic size, two distinct assemblage types of *Miogypsinoides* are recognised within the Early Aquitanian sediments: Type I, possessing a smaller embryo ($D_1 = 120\text{--}135\ \mu\text{m}$) similar to African associations, and Type II, with a larger embryo ($D_1 = 210\text{--}230\ \mu\text{m}$) comparable to European assemblages. These results provide new insight into the biostratigraphic and palaeobiogeographic distribution of Miogypsinids in the Zagros Basin and contribute to refining correlations across the Oligocene–Miocene boundary in the Middle East.

Keywords: Azkand Formation; Oligocene–Miocene; Miogypsinidae; Kirkuk area; Iraq

1. Introduction

The Oligocene carbonate succession of the Azkand Formation in the Kirkuk area of northeastern Iraq provides valuable evidence for the evolutionary development of the *Miogypsinidae*. Biometric analyses of these larger foraminifera offer a clear demonstration of the principle of nepionic acceleration (Tan Sin Hock,

1936), confirming its applicability to the evolution of this group. Most of the *Miogypsina* assemblages investigated in the present study were obtained from the Azkand Formation at the Khabaz Well-3 and Qara Chaugh–Dagh sections, situated approximately 50 km northwest of Kirkuk City in northern Iraq. Fig.1

Fig. 1. Location map of the study area, Kirkuk Oil Fields, northern Iraq (after Buday, 1980).

The evolutionary succession of *Miogypsina* species within the Oligocene strata reveals important deviations from the previously established patterns. In particular, two morphometric units—both related to *Miogypsinoidea bantamensis*—occur in the Aquitanian, rather than a single lineage as reported in earlier studies. These units, designated here as *Miogypsinoidea* Types I and II, represent distinct biometric populations that will be examined in detail. The principal aim of this study is to elucidate the evolutionary patterns of *Miogypsinoidea* within the Azkand Formation and to compare these with evolutionary trends documented in other orbitoidal foraminifera.

The Oligocene–Miocene carbonate succession in northern Iraq comprises several formations that record three distinct depositional cycles corresponding to

reef–back-reef, fore-reef, and basinal facies (Bellen et al., 1959; Ditmar et al., 1971; El-Eissa, 1992). These successions provide a framework for interpreting the palaeoenvironmental evolution of the Kirkuk region and for correlating the *Miogypsinoidea* assemblages with equivalent successions elsewhere in the Zagros Basin.

The present investigation contributes to a more refined understanding of the regional biostratigraphy and palaeobiogeography of *Miogypsinoidea* across the Oligocene–Miocene transition. Through detailed biometric analysis and comparison with established taxonomic frameworks, this study advances the documentation of evolutionary divergence within *Miogypsinoidea* and enhances correlations between African and European bioprovinces. Table 1

Table 1. Age relationships of Oligocene–early Miocene Formations in northern Iraq (after El-Eisa 1992)

Age		Land Ward	Basin Ward
Miocene	Early	N6	Anah Formation
		N5	Azkand Formation
		N4	Ibrahim Formation
Oligocene	Late	N3	Bajwan Formation
		N2	Baba Formation
	Early	N1	Shaurau Formation
		PI9	Shekh Alas Formation
		PI8	Palani Formation

According to (Al-Banna et al. 2010)., the Oligocene-Miocene boundary is located between the Tarjil and Ibrahim formations and two sedimentary cycles represent Oligocene; the first cycle embraces Palani,

Sheikh Alas, and Shurau formations, the second cycle includes Tarjil, Baba and Bajwan formations (Chat-tian), and the third cycle represents Anah, Azkand, and Ibrahim formations (Aquitanian) (fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Tertiary sequence stratigraphy of Iraq. The Oligocene/Miocene boundary was tentatively interpreted as occurring between the Tarjil and Ibrahim sequences. Revised boundary by the positions of Bellen et al. (1959), and maximum flooding surfaces (MFS) of (Sharland et al. 2004) are after Al-Banna (2008).

Stratigraphy of the Studied Area

The stratigraphy of the Kirkuk region records a long and complex history of carbonate sedimentation extending from the Cretaceous to the Miocene. Within this succession, the Oligocene–Miocene carbonates of

the Azkand Formation form one of the principal reservoir intervals, commonly referred to as the “Main Limestone” or “First Pay Zone”. This unit comprises approximately 1,200 feet of fractured biohermal and shoal carbonates of Middle Eocene to Oligocene age. Fig.3

	AGE	FORMATION	LAYER	LAYER THICKNESS (ft)		INTERPRETATION	CYCLES		
				BABA /AMSHE DOME/SADOLE	AYANAH DOME				
TERTIARY	Miocene	Upper Fars				marine sandstone and siltstone	Main Limestone		
		Lower Fars				marine anhydrite and salt			
	Oligocene	Upper	Bajawan ^{dense} _{porous}	A	120	20			back reef reef
			Baba/Akand	B	100	0			forereef
			Tarji	F	F • E • J - 850	0			basin
		Lower	Shurau	C	70	30			back reef-reef
			Sheikh Alas	D	120	0			forereef
	Middle-Upper Eocene	Geraus Pila Spi Avahah ^{dense} _{porous} Jaddala							red beds lagoon shoal basin
			G		0	150			
			H		0	450			
	U. Paleocene Eocene	Kolosh Khurmala Sinjar Aaliji							tiysch lagoon reef to shoal basin
			J		F • E • J - 850				
	CRETACEOUS	Campanian to Maastrichtian	Shiranish						basin
			Tanjero						tiysch

Fig. 3. Stratigraphy and depositional environments of Paleogene strata in the Kirkuk Field (Majid and Veizer, 1986)

Underlying the Main Limestone are the marly limestones of the Shiranish Formation (Campanian–Maastrichtian), representing deep-marine basinal deposits. These are unconformably overlain by the Paleocene Aaliji shales, which act as an effective seal (Ghafor, 1988; ; Al-Shaibani et al., 1993; Al-Fattah et al., 2017, 2018, 2020a, b). The older Qamchuqa Formation (Hauterivian–Albian) forms a thick (1,000–2,000 ft) succession of platform carbonates, which interfinger with basinal marls of the Sarmord Formation. The latter provides a transition to deeper marine environments and acts as a top-seal to the underlying units (Ghafor and Mohialdeen, 2016, 2018; Ghafor et al., 2025).

The Oligocene sequence, particularly the Azkand Formation, occupies a key stratigraphic position between the older Baba, Bajwan, and Tarjil formations of Chattian age and the overlying Ibrahim Formation of Early Miocene (Aquitania) age. According to Al-Banna et al. (2010), two sedimentary cycles can be distinguished within the Oligocene: the first includes the Palani, Sheikh Alas, and Shurau formations, while the

second comprises the Tarjil, Baba, and Bajwan formations (Chattian). The third cycle, encompassing the Anah, Azkand, and Ibrahim formations, represents the Aquitania stage. This framework places the Azkand Formation near the Oligocene–Miocene boundary and highlights its importance in regional sequence stratigraphy.

The type section of the Azkand Formation, first defined by Bellen (1956, in Belle et al., 1959), occurs on the northeastern face of the Azkand Cirque, approximately three miles northeast (N 65° E) of the village of Azkand, on the southern dome of the Qara Chaugh–Dagh structure. The formation consists predominantly of massive, dolomitic, and recrystallised limestones with generally high porosity. Its thickness varies laterally but averages about 100 m (Bellen et al., 1959; Buday, 1980). Table 2-A. The studied outcrops and sub-surface sections—Qara Chaugh–Dagh and Khabaz Well-3—are located 10–20 km southwest to northwest of Kirkuk city, within the Himreen–Makhul sub-zone of the Foothill Zone, belonging to the unstable area of northeastern Iraq (Buday and Jassim, 1987). Table 2-B.

Table 2-A, Lithostratigraphic units of Kirkuk Group subdivisions, based on age, facies, and relationships between reef/back reef-fore reef and offshore facies (Bellen et al. 1959). B, Oligocene lithostratigraphic units and facies (after Ditmar et al. (1971)

A					B				
Age	Sedimentary Cycle	Facies			Age	Sedimentary Cycle	Facies		
		Reef/Back Reef	Reef/Back Reef	Reef/Back Reef			Reef/Back Reef	Fore Reef	Off Shore
Oligocene	Upper	Anah Formation	Azkand Formation	Ibrahim Formation	Oligocene	Upper	Anah Formation	Azkand Formation	Ibrahim Formation
	Middle	Bajwan Formation	Baba Formation	Tarjil Formation		Lower	Shurau Formation	Shekh-Alas Formation	Palani Formation
	Early	Shurau Formation	Shekh-Alas Formation	Serikagni Formation					

Several researchers have examined the Azkand Formation, focusing on its stratigraphy, microfacies, and biostratigraphy (Al-Eisa, 1992; Abid, 1997; Ghafor, 2004, 2022a,b; Ghafor and Muhammad, 2005, 2006, 2007; Muhammad and Ghafor, 2008; Ghafor, 2010; Ghafor et al., 2023, 2024, 2025). These studies collectively emphasise that the Azkand carbonates represent shallow-marine platform deposits that accumulated in an open-shelf environment influenced by both local tectonics and regional eustatic changes.

The younger Fat'ha Formation (Middle Miocene) unconformably overlies the Main Limestone, marking a significant hiatus and reflecting a transition to evaporitic and clastic sedimentation. The youngest Main Limestone units beneath this unconformity are Oligocene in the southeast and Eocene in the northwest of the Kirkuk area (Ghafor and Ahmad, 2019, 2021; Ghafor and Najaflo, 2022; Ghafor et al., 2023, 2024, 2025).

The stratigraphic position of the studied area within the regional geologic framework of northern and northeastern Iraq is presented in Fig. 4. Based on the works of Harland et al. (1990) and El Diasty et al. (2016). The Cretaceous successions have been the subject of extensive studies (e.g., Ghafor, 1988, 1993;

Ghafor et al., 2004; Ghafor & Mohialdeen, 2016, 2018; Ghafor et al., 2012, 2023, 2024; Ghafor & Karim, 1999; Ghafor & Baziany, 2009). Similarly, the Paleogene formations have received significant scholarly attention (Al-Fattah et al., 2017, 2018, 2020a, 2020b; Al-Tae'e et al., 2024a, b, c; Al-Tae'e et al., 2025; Ghafor, 2010; Al-Qayim et al., 2014; Ghafor & Al-Qayim, 2021a, b; Karim & Ghafor, 2021; Al-Qayim & Ghafor, 2022; Ghafor & Muhammad, 2022a, 2023a, b, 2025). The transitional Cretaceous–Paleogene boundary units have also been investigated in detail (Kassab et al., 1986; Ghafor, 1988, 2000, 2020; Al-Shaibani et al., 1993; Sharbazheri et al., 2009, 2011; Al-Nuaimy et al., 2020; Ghafor et al., 2024). Furthermore, Neogene units have been extensively documented (Ghafor, 2004, 2010, 2011, 2014, 2015, 2022a, 2022b; Ghafor & Muhammad, 2005; Muhammad & Ghafor, 2008; Ghafor & Ahmad, 2019, 2021; Ghafor & Najaflo, 2022; Ghafor et al., 2014, 2023, 2025). Oligocene–Miocene sequences are considered equivalent to the Asmari Formation of Iran, as identified by Rashidi et al. (2022, 2023a, b, 2024), Rajabi and Ghafor (2024).

Fig. 4. Stratigraphic correlation chart showing the placement of the Qamchuqa Formation and related units across southern, western, and northern Iraq (Kurdistan Region), based on Harland et al. (1990) and El Diasty et al. (2016). Modifications applied to the Kurdistan area

In the broader geological framework of northern Iraq, the Azkand Formation correlates with the Asmari Formation of Iran, as recognised by Rashidi et al. (2022, 2023a,b, 2024) and Rajabi and Ghafor (2024). These equivalences indicate a regionally continuous shallow-marine carbonate platform extending across the Zagros Basin during the Oligocene–Miocene transition. The Azkand Formation, therefore, provides a crucial record for understanding palaeoenvironmental evolution, regional correlations, and the biogeographic distribution of larger foraminifera during this period.

Materials and Methods

This research investigates the Oligocene–Miocene surface and subsurface carbonate successions within the Low Folded Zone of northeastern Iraq, focusing on two representative sections: the Khabaz Well-3 and the

Qara Chaugh–Dagh outcrop. These localities provide complementary exposures of the Azkand Formation and allow a comparative analysis of its stratigraphic and palaeontological characteristics.

A total of 76 limestone samples were collected from fossiliferous intervals, including 20 from the Khabaz Well-3 and 26 from the Qara Chaugh–Dagh section. The Khabaz Well-3 succession has a total thickness of approximately 117 m, while the Qara Chaugh–Dagh section measures around 26 m. Both sequences exhibit closely comparable lithological and faunal characteristics, providing a reliable basis for integrated analysis.

The identification and taxonomic classification of the larger foraminifera were performed through thin-

section petrography using standard polarising microscopy. Specimens were identified according to the systematic frameworks established in previous works (Ghafor, 2022a,b; Ghafor and Najafloo, 2022; Rajabi and Ghafor, 2024; Ghafor et al., 2024, 2025; Serra-Kiel et al., 2016).

Lithological logging and detailed field observations were conducted to record variations in sedimentary facies, grain size, sorting, fossil content, and microfacies architecture. The microfacies analysis focused on distinguishing depositional textures, identifying bioclast composition, and interpreting palaeoenvironmental conditions. Quantitative assessment of *Miogypsinid* abundance and distribution within each unit allowed recognition of vertical and lateral variations in assemblage composition.

The biometric study followed established methodologies for measuring morphological parameters of *Mi-*

ogypsinidae (Drooger, 1993; Raju, 1974). Fig.5. Parameters such as the protoconch and deutoconch diameters (D_1 , D_2), number of nepionic chambers (X), and angular relationships (γ , α , β , V) were systematically recorded to evaluate intraspecific variation and evolutionary trends. The morphometric data were subsequently processed statistically to distinguish biometric groups and identify potential evolutionary lineages.

This integrated methodological approach—combining field observations, petrographic examination, and biometric analysis—provides a comprehensive framework for interpreting the stratigraphic distribution, taxonomy, and evolutionary relationships of *Miogypsinidae* within the Azkand Formation. The resulting dataset forms the basis for reconstructing depositional environments and evaluating regional correlations across the Oligocene–Miocene transition in the Zagros Basin.

Fig. 5: Schematic drawing the median sections of the embryonic-nepionic stage of *Miogypsinidae* illustrating the derivation of (α , β and γ). 1 = protoconch, 2 = deutoconch. 1 and 2 constitute the embryonic stage; chambers around the embryonic stage (dotted in figs. a, b) constitute the nepionic stage. P1 = first principal auxiliary chamber, P2=second principal auxiliary chamber; a = accessory auxiliary chamber, c = closing chamber. (after Raju, 1974 and Drooger, 1993).

Review of Previous Research on *Miogypsinidae*

The genus *Miogypsina* was first established by Sacco in 1893, with *Nummulites irregularis* Michelotti (1841) designated as the type species. Since then, more than fifty species, subspecies, and varieties have been described within the family *Miogypsinidae*. The extensive literature on this group reflects over a century of investigation into its taxonomy, morphology, and evolutionary history.

Between 1893 and 1936, numerous researchers contributed to the description of *Miogypsinidae* spe-

cies, including Van der Vlerk (1929). These early studies, while taxonomically rich, gave limited attention to phylogenetic relationships.

A major conceptual advance was achieved by Tan Sin Hok (1936, 1937), who introduced a theoretical framework for understanding phylogenetic trends in the *Miogypsinidae*. Based on his study of Indonesian material, Tan recognised five fundamental types of nepionic chamber arrangements—*complanata*, *borneensis*, *ecuadorensis*, *bifida*, and *indonesiensis*. He argued that these developmental types were fundamental to understanding evolutionary relationships within the group. Tan's concept of "nepionic acceleration," describing

the progressive shortening of early ontogenetic stages in evolutionary time, became a cornerstone of later research.

Subsequent investigators refined and expanded Tan's approach. Drooger (1952) applied statistical methods to American *Miogypsinidae*, introducing the "population concept," which assumed that individuals within a single sample generally belonged to a single, homogeneous population unless discontinuities in morphometric parameters indicated otherwise. He numerically expressed morphological variation through a series of quantitative measurements and used statistical analysis to distinguish between closely related taxa. His subsequent work (1953–1966) on European and Indonesian *Miogypsinidae* contributed greatly to understanding phylogenetic trends in the group.

Other significant contributions include those of Souaya (1961), who applied similar morphometric methods to Indian and Egyptian material, respectively. Their results demonstrated that *Miogypsinidae* are valuable tools for intercontinental correlation of Oligocene–Miocene strata. Although Drooger's statistical approach was generally considered sound (Cole, 1957), it faced criticism for being time-consuming and for relying on stratigraphic assumptions not always verifiable in field conditions (Adams, 1970).

Cole (1938) carried out extensive investigations of American and West Pacific *Miogypsinidae*. Initially adopting a typological approach, he later consolidated numerous species into a few broadly defined taxa—reducing the American species to five in 1957 and later to three (1964, 1967). While claiming a biological species concept, Cole's later work still reflected typological tendencies, sometimes splitting homogeneous populations.

In contrast, Hanzawa (1940–1965) followed a more rigid typological approach in his studies of West Pacific assemblages. He employed several measurable parameters—including the apical–frontal angle (A–P angle), number of juvenile whorls, number of septa per whorl, and peri-prolocular chamber ranking—combined with Tan's nepionic types, to differentiate as many as forty-six species. This extreme "splitting" approach contrasted with Cole's "lumping" tendency, illustrating the long-standing debate within *Miogypsinid* taxonomy between morphological and biological species concepts.

Research in Iraq on *Miogypsinidae* has been comparatively recent. The first systematic investigations were conducted in the Kirkuk area and surrounding regions by Ghafor (2004) and subsequently expanded in several studies (Ghafor and Muhammad, 2005, 2007; Muhammad and Ghafor, 2008; Ghafor and Ahmad, 2021; Ghafor, 2022; Ghafor et al., 2023, 2024, 2025). These works established the regional biostratigraphic distribution of *Miogypsinidae* in northeastern Iraq and provided key data for understanding the Oligocene–Miocene transition in the Zagros Basin.

Overall, the history of *Miogypsinidae* research illustrates a gradual shift from purely descriptive taxonomy toward a quantitative, evolutionary framework. The integration of morphometrics, stratigraphic distribution, and palaeobiogeography now provides a robust

basis for using *Miogypsinidae* as high-resolution biostratigraphic and palaeoenvironmental indicators in carbonate successions of the Tethyan realm.

Methods of Investigation

The biometric investigation of *Miogypsinidae* in this study follows the quantitative and morphometric approaches established by Drooger (1964), with several modifications to suit the available material. Only the most diagnostic parameters that define species and sub-generic variation are considered here.

Measured Parameters

1. Number of Nepionic Chambers (X):

This represents the total number of nepionic chambers within the initial spiral, excluding the two embryonic chambers but including the closing chamber, when present.

2. Angular Parameter (γ):

The γ value quantifies the orientation of the nepiont relative to the test axis. It is defined by two intersecting line segments—one connecting the centres of the protoconch and deutoconch and extending towards the apical point of the test (the apical–frontal line). The zero point of the γ -scale is assigned to configurations where the two lines coincide in individuals with one whorl or fewer. A positive γ indicates that the first principal auxiliary chamber points towards the frontal margin of the test; a negative γ denotes the opposite, measured by rotating the embryonic line segment in the direction of coiling until it coincides with the apical–frontal line.

3. Arc Lengths (α and β):

Parameter α represents the arc length of the protoconch circumference underlying the shorter spiral, while β corresponds to the arc length underlying both protoconchal spirals.

4. Symmetry Index (V):

This dimensionless ratio expresses the degree of symmetry of the protoconchal spirals and is calculated as:

$$V = \frac{200\alpha}{\beta}$$

The scale ranges from 0 to 100, where higher values indicate greater symmetry.

5. Protoconch Diameter (D₁):

The maximum diameter of the protoconch, measured perpendicular to the embryonic line, including half the thickness of the chamber wall.

6. Deutoconch Diameter (D₂):

The maximum diameter of the deutoconch, measured parallel to the line used for D₁.

7. Percentage of Specimens with Dual Principal Auxiliary Chambers (P):

This parameter expresses the proportion of individuals possessing two principal auxiliary chambers within the population.

Analytical Procedures

All measurements were taken on oriented thin sections of well-preserved specimens under a polarising microscope at magnifications of 25× to 50×. The morphological parameters were quantified using a calibrated ocular micrometer, and each measurement was repeated to minimise observational error. Data were

statistically processed to determine mean values, standard deviations, and coefficients of variability ($V(D_1)$, $V(D_2)$, V_x), which were used to assess population homogeneity and distinguish between morphometric groups.

Scatter diagrams of D_1 against D_2 , X , and γ were prepared to visualise morphological relationships and to detect potential clustering indicative of discrete biometric populations. These graphical analyses were complemented by frequency histograms to identify unimodal or bimodal distributions within the datasets.

The combination of quantitative biometric methods and statistical evaluation provides a rigorous

framework for assessing intraspecific variability, evolutionary trends, and potential lineage differentiation within *Miogypsina* and *Miogypsinoides*.

Results

6.1 Lithology and Microfacies of the Studied Sections

The investigated successions from the Khabaz Well-3 and Qara Chaugh–Dagh sections consist predominantly of fossiliferous limestones rich in *Miogypsinidae*. Four principal microfacies have been recognised based on textural characteristics, faunal composition, and sedimentary structures. Figs. 6 and 7.

Fig. 6. A – Lithostratigraphic section of the Azkand Formation in the Khabaz well-3 section. B – Lithostratigraphic section of the Azkand Formation in the Qara Chaugh Dagh section.

Fig. 7: a- *Miogypsinoides complanata*, Unit I, sample 7, Khabaz well-3 section, Azkand Formation. (30X), oriented section, b- *Miogypsinoides complanata*, Unit II, sample 8, Qara Chuagh-Dagh section, Azkand Formation. (30X), oriented section, c- *Miogypsinoides complanata*, Unit I, sample 12, Qara Chuagh- Dagh section, Azkand Formation. (30X), oriented section, d- *Miogypsinoides formosensis*, Unit I, sample 17, Khabaz well-3 section, Azkand Formation. (30X), oriented section, e- *Miogypsinoides formosensis*, Unit III, sample 16, Qara Chuagh-Dagh section, Azkand Formation. (30X), oriented section, f- *Miogypsinoides bantamensis*, Unit II, sample 19, Qara Chuagh -Dagh section, Azkand Formation. (30X), oriented section, g- *Miogypsinoides bantamensis*, Unit IV, sample 38, Khabaz well-3 section, Azkand Formation. (30X), oriented section, h- *Miogypsinoides gunteri*, Unit IV, sample 48, Khabaz well-3 section, Azkand Formation. (30X), oriented section, i- *Miogypsinoides gunteri*, Unit IV, sample 26, Qara Chaugh- Dagh section, Azkand Formation. (30X), oriented section.

6.1.1 Unit I – Fine Bioclastic Smaller Foraminiferal Packstone

This basal unit comprises fine- to medium-grained bioclastic packstone, occasionally containing larger bioclasts and localised bioturbation. The thickness varies between approximately 10 and 48 metres. The lower part includes algal fragments and encrusting foraminifera, whereas the upper part is characterised by an increased abundance of *Miogypsinids*. The microfacies indicates deposition in a shallow, open-marine environment with moderate energy conditions.

6.1.2 Unit II – Fine- to Coarse-Grained Larger Foraminiferal Packstone to Grainstone

Unit II consists of fine- to very coarse-grained packstone grading into grainstone. Individual grains occasionally exceed 5 mm in diameter and exhibit poor sorting. The thickness ranges from 5 to 17 metres. The microfacies is dominated by large benthic foraminifera, particularly *Miogypsinoides*, suggesting accumulation in a high-energy shoal or back-reef setting.

6.1.3 Unit III – Fine- to Very Coarse-Grained Larger Foraminiferal Packstone to Grainstone

This unit exhibits a fining-upward trend, composed mainly of fine- to very coarse-grained packstone and subordinate grainstone. The presence of both large and small benthic foraminifera indicates deposition in a transitional environment between inner- and middle-

shelf settings. The observed variations in grain size and sorting reflect fluctuating hydrodynamic energy.

6.1.4 Unit IV – Fine- to Coarse-Grained Bioclastic Packstone to Boundstone

The uppermost unit consists of fine- to medium-grained packstone with scattered larger bioclasts and minor bioturbation. Its thickness varies from 6 to 42 metres. The lithofacies suggests deposition in a relatively shallow, agitated setting with local biogenic framework development.

The vertical succession of facies from packstone to boundstone reflects a gradual shallowing trend through time, consistent with progradation of a carbonate platform margin.

6.2 Assemblage Heterogeneity

The lower part of the Khabaz Well-3 (Unit III, Sample 42) and the corresponding level in the Qara Chaugh–Dagh section (Sample 18) contain mixed assemblages characterised by the coexistence of *Miogypsina* s.s. and *Miogypsinoides*. Specimens with lateral chambers represent *Miogypsina* s.s., whereas those lacking such features correspond to *Miogypsinoides*.

Most of the remaining intervals in both sections (Units II–IV) consist almost entirely of *Miogypsinoides*, reflecting its dominance in the later stages of Azkand carbonate deposition. Some specimens could not be confidently assigned to a subgenus due to poor preservation and dolomitisation. Figs 8 and 9

Legend:

- D₁: The maximum diameter of the protoconch
- D₂: The large diameter of the deutoconch
- X: The total number of nepionic chambers
- γ: The angular parameter is quantitative measure of the orientation of the nepiont in the foraminiferal test

Fig. 8. Histogram of D₁, D₂, X and γ of *Miogypsina s.s.*, and *Miogypsinoides* and the Khabaz well-3 Section, Azkand Formation.

Legend:

- D₁: The maximum diameter of the protoconch
 - D₂: The large diameter of the deutoconch
 - X: The total number of nepionic chambers
 - γ: The angular parameter is quantitative measure of the orientation of the nepion in the foraminiferal test
- Miogypsinoides I*
 - Miogypsinoides II*
 - Miogypsinina s.s.*

Fig. 9. Histogram of D₁, D₂, X and γ of *Miogypsinina s.s.*, and *Miogypsinoides* and the Qara Chaugh Dagh section, Azkand Formation.

Biometric analysis of these assemblages reveals considerable variability. Coefficients of variation for *Miogypsinina s.s.* (VD₁ = 35–36) and *Miogypsinoides* (VD₁ ≈ 28–30) indicate inhomogeneous populations. Scatter diagrams of D₁ plotted against D₂, X, and γ demonstrate overlapping morphometric fields between the two groups. In certain samples (Khabaz 42; Qara Chaugh 18), *Miogypsinoides* individuals form two distinct clusters based on protoconch diameter, suggesting

the presence of two separate biometric groups: (Figs 10–13)

- **Group I:** Small protoconch (D₁ = 120–135 μm)
- **Group II:** Large protoconch (D₁ = 210–230 μm)

Fig. 10. Scatter diagram of D_1 - X , D_2 - X and D_1 - γ diagrams of *Miogypsina s.s.*, and *Miogypsinoidea* in sample 18 of the Qara Chaugh Dagh section, Azkand Formation. Dashed line is scatter periphery of *Miogypsina s.s.*, individuals, solid line is scatter periphery of *Miogypsinoidea* individuals.

Fig. 11. Scatter diagram of D_1 - X , D_2 - X and D_1 - γ diagrams of *Miogypsinina s.s.*, and *Miogypsinoides* in sample 48 of the Khabaz Well-3 section, Azkand Formation. Dashed line is scatter periphery of *Miogypsinina s.s.* individuals, solid line is scatter periphery of *Miogypsinoides* individuals.

Fig. 12. Scatter diagram of $D1-\gamma$, $X-D1$, $X-\gamma$, and $D1-D2-X$ and diagrams of the *Miogypsinoides* specimens in the samples (38, 39, 40, 41, 42, and 43) of Unit III, in the Khabaz well-3 section, Azkand Formation.

Fig. 13. Scatter diagram of $D1-\gamma$, $X-D1$, $X-\gamma$, and $D1-D2-X$ and diagrams of the *Miogypsinoides* specimens in the samples (17, 18, 20, and 26) of Unit III, in the Qara Chaugh Dagh section, Azkand Formation.

These clusters correspond to *Miogypsinoidea* *ogypsina* s.s. and *Miogypsinoidea* I indicates transitional morphologies and potential phylogenetic relationships. Table 3-7

Table 3- A-Coefficient of variability for *Miogypsina*, *Miogypsinoidea*, in sample 45 of the Khabaz well-3 section. B- Coefficient of variability for *Miogypsina*, *Miogypsinoidea*, in sample 20 of the Qara Chaugh Dagh section

A				B			
Genus Name	VD ₁	VD ₂	V _x	Genus Name	VD ₁	VD ₂	V _x
<i>Miogypsina</i> s.s	36.4	31.3	13.6	<i>Miogypsina</i> s.s	29.6	29.3	11.6
<i>Miogypsinoidea</i> I	28.4	28.01	10.45	<i>Miogypsinoidea</i> I	29.4	29.01	11.45
<i>Miogypsinoidea</i> II	10.02	08.03	11.56	<i>Miogypsinoidea</i> II	9.72	09.73	11.34

Table 4-Basic statistics for *Miogypsinoidea* of Units (I, II, III, and IV) in the Khabaz well-3 section.

Sample No.	X̄	N	γ̄	N	D ₁	N	D ₂	N
49	12.3	13	-106.5	13	128.1	13	139	13
43	12.8	15	-102.3	15	137.6	15	148.1	15
42	12.3	18	-129.5	18	138.4	18	149.5	18
41	12.3	12	-96.3	12	144.9	12	154.66	12
40	12.6	15	-106.9	15	136.4	15	150.1	15
39	10.52	15	-110	15	141.3	15	151	15
38	12.3	18	-134.9	18	132.4	18	147.2	18
25	15.1	17	-157.1	17	227.2	17	237.6	17
23	15.3	18	-150.3	18	231.3	18	241.9	18
16	19.3	15	-171.6	15	236.4	15	247.2	15
7	18.2	14	-174.7	14	242.6	14	251.8	14

Table 5-Basic statistics for *Miogypsinoidea* of Units (I, II, III, and IV) in the Qara Chaugh-Dagh section

Sample No.	X̄	N	γ̄	N	D ₁	N	D ₂	N
26	11.54	12	-166.8	12	154.1	12	155	12
21	11.6	14	-130.6	14	133.6	14	144.1	14
20	11.7	15	-132.5	15	132.4	15	142.5	15
18	11.6	18	-118.3	18	127.3	18	139.66	18
17	11.9	15	-142.9	15	122.4	15	139.1	15
12	11.6	14	-145.4	14	134.4	14	143	14
6	19.8	12	-145.4	12	250.64	12	259.2	12
3	19.1	12	-160.1	12	257.2	12	265.6	12

Table 6- Basic statistics for *Miogypsina* s.s. of Units (I, II, III, and IV) in the Khabaz Well-3 section.

Sample No.	X̄	N	γ̄	N	D ₁	N	D ₂	N
49	9.53	12	-122.5	12	117.1	12	130	12
43	9.4	11	-98.3	11	135.6	11	142.1	11
42	10.3	15	-105.5	15	153.4	15	184.5	15
41	10.3	14	-49.3	14	144.9	14	192.66	14
40	10.6	13	-98.9	13	133.4	13	146.1	13
39	10.52	11	-112.3	11	136.3	11	144	11
38	9.3	12	-106.9	12	134.4	12	143.2	12

Table 7- Basic statistics for *Miogypsina* s.s. of Units (I, II, III, and IV) in Qara Chaugh-Dagh section.

Sample No.	\bar{X}	N	γ	N	D ₁	N	D ₂	N
26	9.3	12	-186.5	12	108.1	12	118	12
21	9.8	11	-140.3	11	141.6	11	152.1	11
20	9.3	15	-131.5	15	148.4	15	158.5	15
18	10.3	14	-127.3	14	138.9	14	156.66	14
17	9.6	13	-91.9	13	131.4	13	151.1	13
12	10.52	11	-148.3	11	148.3	11	165	11

6.3 Evolutionary Development and Biometric Interpretation

Two distinct *Miogypsinoidea* populations—both morphologically related to *M. bantamensis*—coexist with *Miogypsina gunteri-tani* in the Aquitanian carbonates of the Azkand Formation. The principal distinction between *Miogypsinoidea* I and II lies in embryonic size, with Type I displaying a smaller protoconch (mean D₁ ≈ 120 μm) and Type II exhibiting a larger one (mean D₁ ≈ 220 μm). Nepionic configurations show only minor differences.

The stratigraphic distribution of *Miogypsinoidea* I extends into the Late Aquitanian, where it occurs alongside *Miogypsina gunteri* and *M. tani*. Within this interval, *Miogypsinoidea* I shows a slight reduction in the mean number of nepionic chambers ($X = 11-12$) compared with its early Aquitanian ancestors ($X = 13-14$). Despite this shift, both *Miogypsinoidea* I and II maintain consistent nepionic patterns across the studied succession.

Morphologically, *Miogypsinoidea* I closely resembles primitive *Miogypsina gunteri*, whereas *Miogypsinoidea* II overlaps with older species such as *M. complanata* and *M. formosensis*. The simultaneous occurrence of both types in the Aquitanian is rare in the global record and may reflect distinct ecological or biogeographical origins.

It is proposed that *Miogypsinoidea bantamensis* and its derivatives favoured hard substrates in relatively shallow environments, while *Miogypsina* s.s. and *Miogypsinoidea* I were more typical of slightly deeper, open-marine settings. The relative abundance of Type II in the upper part of the succession suggests adaptation to shallower-water conditions.

These results support the hypothesis that early *Miogypsinoidea* diverged into two evolutionary branches near the Chattian–Aquitanian boundary: one retaining massive side walls (*Miogypsinoidea* line) and another developing lateral chamber complexes (*Miogypsina* s.s. line). The observed biometric differentiation likely reflects ecological adaptation rather than purely phylogenetic divergence.

Comparison with European and African *Miogypsinoidea* assemblages (Drooger and Raju, 1973; De Mulder, 1975) suggests that *Miogypsinoidea* I corresponds to African-type associations (e.g., Egypt, Morocco), whereas *Miogypsinoidea* II shows closer affinity to European forms. This supports a palaeobiogeographical model involving south-to-north migration of *Miogypsinoidea* I during the early Aquitanian, representing influxes from the African subprovince into the northeastern Arabian platform. Fig.14

Fig. 14 : D₁- \bar{X} diagram of *Miogypsinoidea* in the Khabaz well-3 and Qarah Chauq Dagh sections. Dashed lines separate European assemblages of *Miogypsinoidea* from assemblages of African origin and assemblages from Sicily. (Literature data from Drooger and Raju, 1973 and De Mulder, 1975).

Conclusions

The Azkand Formation in the Kirkuk area of northeastern Iraq provides an important record of *Miogypsinid* evolution across the Oligocene–Miocene (Chattian–Aquitania) transition. The detailed biometric analysis undertaken in this study reveals significant evolutionary, stratigraphic, and palaeoenvironmental insights.

1. Species Distribution:

The oldest *Miogypsinoides* species within the Azkand Formation are represented by *M. complanata* and *M. formosensis*, which occur in the lower parts of the succession. These species are associated with early *Miogypsina gunteri* forms, marking the transitional interval between the Late Oligocene and Early Miocene.

2. Assemblage Composition:

Early Miocene assemblages dominated by *Miogypsina gunteri–tani* are frequently accompanied by *Miogypsinoides*, particularly forms closely related to *M. bantamensis*. The presence of mixed *Miogypsina* s.s. and *Miogypsinoides* assemblages in several horizons demonstrates evolutionary continuity between the two lineages.

3. Biometric Trends:

The mean values of the nepionic parameter (X) display a progressive reduction from *Miogypsinoides* species ($X = 13–17$) in the lower Azkand Formation to *Miogypsina gunteri–tani* ($X = 9–11$) in the upper part. This trend supports the principle of nepionic acceleration and indicates gradual morphological simplification through evolutionary time.

4. Biometric Grouping:

Two distinct *Miogypsinoides* assemblage types are identified in the Aquitania strata based on embryonic size:

- **Type I:** Small embryo ($D_1 = 120–135 \mu\text{m}$), comparable to African associations.
- **Type II:** Large embryo ($D_1 = 210–230 \mu\text{m}$), resembling European assemblages.

These coexisting forms suggest palaeobiogeographical differentiation within the *Miogypsinidae* and possibly reflect migration or parallel evolution within distinct ecological niches.

5. Palaeoenvironmental and Biogeographical Implications:

The *Miogypsinid* assemblages of the Azkand Formation reflect deposition in a shallow, open-marine platform environment. The distribution of biometric types indicates that *Miogypsinoides* II preferred shallower, higher-energy conditions, while *Miogypsinoides* I and *Miogypsina* s.s. occupied slightly deeper habitats. The simultaneous occurrence of both types within the Aquitania carbonates is interpreted as the result of south-to-north migration of *Miogypsinoides* I from the African subprovince into the Zagros Basin.

6. Evolutionary Significance:

The co-occurrence of *Miogypsinoides* I and II represents an evolutionary bifurcation near the Chattian–Aquitania boundary, where one branch evolved towards *Miogypsina* s.s. through the development of lateral chamber complexes, and the other retained the massive side walls characteristic of *Miogypsinoides*.

This differentiation was likely driven by ecological adaptation to varying substrate and depth conditions on the carbonate platform.

In summary, the *Miogypsinidae* assemblages of the Azkand Formation document a crucial evolutionary phase in the development of larger foraminifera in the Tethyan realm. The biometric and taxonomic data from this study enhance regional biostratigraphic correlations, clarify palaeobiogeographical connections between Africa and Eurasia, and contribute to a more refined understanding of Oligocene–Miocene carbonate system evolution in northern Iraq.

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